

Revisiting Chandigarh: The Question of Preservation and Intervention in the Sector 17 Central Chouk*

Billboards crowd the premises of the railway station. Traditionally frowned upon by the Chandigarh Administration¹, they have been concentrated here under the protection of the Northern Railway. At the road entrances to the Union Territory² stunted reproductions of Le Corbusier's Open Hand symbol sport the civic boast: 'WELCOME TO CITY BEAUTIFUL.'

Nothing much has changed, yet now, returning very occasionally to Chandigarh,³ I do not find it a cosy experience of recognition: rather, my mind goes back to the impressions of a few brief visits made some years before the time when I lived and worked there. Uninstructed, I was uncertain about what to make of my surroundings, though not displeased with them: the ubiquity of modernist architecture and the absence of the visual clutter of other Indian cities; the wide, often barren spaces and vast green but often empty-looking parks; those long blank-walled roads; the feeling — I do not have a particularly good sense of direction anyway — of being unable to locate oneself.

Being there officially, I was each time shown the sights by obliging junior members of whatever Department of the Punjab or Haryana Government was concerned with my visit: I would be driven through the Capitol, shown the lake and, most importantly, Nek Chand's Rock Garden. The Rock Garden, a small miracle created out of waste, scrap, local materials — and plenty of cement — by a once

humble employee of the Engineering Department, is Chandigarh's only really well-known tourist attraction, the only thing here that people not specially interested in modernist architecture come to see: it is another kind of modernity, having nothing whatsoever to do with Le Corbusier, yet not out of place in his city. I fancy it as the location of one sequence in the chase across town at the climax of a thriller film: the end must of course come somewhere in the moonscape⁴ grounds of the Capitol after the camera has exploited the drama of its great buildings — action among the forest of columns in the foyer of the Assembly, on the ramp and rooftop of the Secretariat, in the tall shadows of the High Court portico, under the Open Hand monument as it rotates ever so slowly... Directed right, the camera's eye should discover in Chandigarh a visual personality that is sufficiently self-consistent, distinctive, stylish — and strange — for some slick cinematography of that genre: though a certain amount of scruffy Indian reality would have to be edited out.

Later, while working in Chandigarh and charged with administrative responsibility, the lens through which it seemed proper to view the city was that of its famous Master Plan. A tour de force it was when first expounded to me by the Urban Planning Department, marrying art with professional omniscience, inspired in its neat appropriation of the natural features of the site as it fitted the gradual slope southward from the hills between two framing choes⁵, damming one of them to create the lake and turning a third choe into the Leisure Valley. In the Master Plan that he drew, and in the Statute of the Land and the Edict of Chandigarh, Le Corbusier had left us a code of almost scriptural authority. Chandigarh became a sort of designer city and, as such, a functional and artistic unity: tamper too much with any of its elements and you might put the whole at risk. First, there is the ten-mile deep green belt on the periphery. This is essential because "Chandigarh is a Government city with a precise goal and consequently a precise quality of inhabitants. On this presumption, the city has not to be a big city (metropolis) — it must not lose its definition"⁶. Next, there is the hierarchical 'sept voies' road system. Third, there is the system of zoning which, together with the road system, creates the self-contained residential sector crossed horizontally by the (V-4) market street (with shopping on only one side of the street) and vertically by a continuous green belt. 'The fundamental principle is that never a door will open on the surrounding V-3s [inter-sector fast-traffic roads]: they must be separated from the sector by a blind wall all along.' Fourth, there is the whole panoply of architectural and visual controls. These include 'Full Architectural Control' in some cases; in others con-

trol on the system of construction and architectural treatment of the exterior, except in the case of large private housing plots; 'frame' or facade control in the case of smaller houses in terrace formation; standard designs for gates and boundary walls; the 'no statue' rule and very strict controls on advertisements. Sixth, we could mention the city's trees and gardens, very systematically planted in Phase I in the 1960s under M.S. Randhawa and now a part of the city's image. Finally, there is Chandigarh's stock of modernist buildings; Le Corbusier's Capitol deserves to be completed and made a world heritage site, but the city's riches also include a large number of workaday buildings by the original team of architects and their successors. The effect of the controls and the stock of existing buildings, taken together, still give Chandigarh a consistency of style and appearance that is unique among Indian cities.

Yet one found that these elements, and the unity they were intended to make up, could be remarkably invisible to people not trained to look at the city through those same spectacles. Nor is it the case merely that people fail to perceive the Master Plan through the city: conversely, you do not see the city through the Master Plan. It does not at all parallel the relationship of architectural plans to their buildings: the scale is very different and the subject of depiction infinitely more complex. And it is static: therefore, over time, it distorts our cognisance of the developing real-life city, our normative spectacles filtering out too much of empirical reality. (What the plan leaves out has no business to be there anyway.) Thus the Master Plan records an ideal that the city was originally built to match, but never quite did, which now survives increasingly as myth. In Chandigarh it remains a powerful myth both because of the emotional investment that has been made in it and because of the interests that sustain it.

For many the Chandigarh project still recalls an era of young-nation hope and enthusiasm and its realization, in the rural Punjab of the 1950s, did have an epic quality.⁷

Nehru's words have become a local cliché, but have not lost their ring: 'Let this be a new town symbolic of the freedom of India, unfettered by the traditions of the past... an expression of the nation's faith in the future'. And the hubris of modernism was a concurrent source of energy. Le Corbusier famously said there could not be an especially Indian architecture when we had adopted trousers and democracy. Nehru (rejecting trousers) remained an enthusiastic modernist:

'The past was good – but only when it was the present. We cannot bring it forward and put up a Gothic cathedral and call it a railway terminus... I like the creative approach, not being tied down to

what was done by our forefathers but thinking in new terms, of light and air and ground and water and human beings. Therefore, Chandigarh is of enormous importance.'⁸

So these also became formative, exciting times for the architectural profession in India, creating an interest and awareness, and hence opportunities, hitherto lacking. 'Suddenly India was centre-stage', Charles Correa says, speaking of the impact of the Capitol. 'This was adrenaline indeed. ...we got the extraordinary opportunity to be at the cutting-edge of where it was all happening.'⁹

All that is obviously the original source of Chandigarh's enduring mystique. But nowadays there is surprisingly little popular, non-professional appreciation for its architecture. Those in authority are often unimpressed when reminded how well known Chandigarh is: the Department of Culture in the Central Government could not be persuaded to take seriously the idea of proposing any part of Chandigarh for UNESCO listing as a World Heritage Site. One was not able to drum up much enthusiasm for the idea of finally building the Governor's Palace.¹⁰ Worse, the Punjab and Haryana Governments cannot be persuaded to stop glazing over the facades of the Secretariat to gain just a few more feet of working space – when I last saw it half the building had been covered. One wonders whether the modernist aesthetic was not at best a transient fashion here, which continued long after its time to be imposed, in a closely regulated urban regime, by the fidelity of its bureaucracy: Almost invariably – starting with the Punjab Raj Bhavan¹¹ – the interiors contrast noticeably with the buildings themselves. People want glitz, their taste runs indiscriminatingly to the ornate. The loosening of controls is received with a sense of liberation: 'The faces of residential houses in the city and its outskirts have changed a lot and seem to be getting better. Grandeur is the watchword today.'¹² This 'grandeur' is expressed in entrance gates weighing more than a tonne with 'a large variety of intricate designs'. An architect is quoted as saying that he uses pitched roofs and jutting open balconies, admittedly inappropriate for the climate, 'mostly for decoration and for the sake of having something unique... and getting a spectacular effect'. A property dealer welcomes the new liberty: 'It's all part of showing off. We wear good clothes because we want to show off, so why not the same with our houses?'¹³

So love of its architecture is not central to the love of Chandigarh. It is very relevant that our preferences have been shaped by British-Indian bungalows with their vast private compounds in the cantonments and 'civil lines' that the British appended to Indian towns, a form which found its apotheosis in the splendid Bungalow Zone (as it is now called)

of Lutyens's New Delhi. Chandigarh⁴ often passes for more of the same in modernist dress, and not without reason:

*'Of course we pretend that our defence [of Chandigarh] is based on a pious reverence for the ideas of the Great Man. But it is not – it is based on the (near-pathological) awe we have for the lifestyle that prevailed in the cantonment areas which the British created ...long forgotten are the indigenous typologies, e.g. the haveli, wonderful examples of which exist in all our towns and cities...multi-storeyed houses built around courtyards, in patterns which make complete sense both socially and culturally, as well as from considerations of climate and urban form.'*¹⁵

That is undoubtedly true, and Chandigarh seems willing to find intellectual comfort not merely in Le Corbusier but eclectically in any term that strikes the right emotional chords, 'Garden City' and 'City Beautiful' together. But it is material that Chandigarh, contrasted with the squalor, futh, confusion and mismanagement increasingly associated with most Indian cities, is widely respected as a haven of (relative) order, tranquillity and sanitation. That sustains the Chandigarh mystique: the authorities can still get away with a lot of regulation, sometimes cussed and bloody-minded, on the strength of the threat, 'You don't want Chandigarh to become like Delhi, do you?' The best urban living in India is thought of as clean, green and genteel: you would have to be an intellectual to prefer anything else. Most of the walled city of Delhi, with its dense urban fabric, vivid colours, mixed land use, its traditional life and its narrow lanes, and its considerable wealth and economic activity, has long been notified officially, under the relevant law in force,¹⁶ as 'slum'; its population has been declining for a couple of decades as residents move out and convert their properties to commercial use. One loses count of the number of people asserting that there is no city like Chandigarh: of what avail might it be to tell them to read, say, Jane Jacobs?

But Chandigarh is more than a city of bungalows: it made important innovations, it seriously tried to improve housing standards for its humblest planned residents – and there are stories of how high ranking officials thought their houses and lawns were too small! Sector 22, which was the first sector to be developed, contains some very innovative and attractive housing for subordinate Government employees. And this was the first Indian city to envisage running water and water closets in every house. In Chandigarh the bungalow paradigm, inherited from the British Raj, has got conflated with the hygienic modernism (concern for fresh air and sanitation, sun, space and verdure) that can more

legitimately be read into the planners' intentions, and this has to be understood in the context of the economic, technological and social environment of the India of nearly half a century ago. Its low-rise architecture and low densities, which have become such an integral part of its image, were not what would have been expected from Le Corbusier and in fact his early sketches for Sector 17 as well as for the Capitol had included high-rise buildings, but he had to compromise here: Maxwell Fry described the project as 'a frontier undertaking carried out with men, women, children, donkeys and camels in place of high overheads and loads of equipment' and as 'a poor state's capital in two dimensions, with no two-grade intersections in our lifetime,' and wrote of the compulsion to 'eschew costly expedients for dealing with traffic and concentrating the occupation of land that distinguished Brasilia'. Chandigarh is thus the modernist city that it was possible to build in the particular place and time that it was built.

Is it worth discussing change, then? Visiting professionals and academics are sometimes nonplussed by the hostility they encounter when they fail to accord to Chandigarh the reverence of its conservatives.¹⁷ But they too may be looking at the city through the distorting lenses of their own preconceptions, which may merely be more currently fashionable than those of their outraged interlocutors. What are we to make, in particular, of those who seem to think the city's most pressing need is simply to present a more interesting face to them? It is too easy to reduce what was a genuine insight into the values of urban life, to an aesthetic rule of thumb: if you see plenty of people in close proximity, you have 'urbanity'. So we get the expert who takes a stroll about the city and says, Ah, not enough urbanity, let's put some housing in Sector 17 (the Town Centre) so we see more people!

Le Corbusier spoke of 'a city offering all amenities to the poorest of its citizens to lead a dignified life'¹⁸ but the most telling criticisms of Chandigarh have been made on behalf of its poorer inhabitants, for its failure to do just that.¹⁹ A fifth of the population are squatters, another fifth live in resettlement camps put up outside the area of the Master Plan in a series of attempted one-time solutions to the problem of unauthorized housing.

Certainly, there has not been nearly enough low-cost housing, and most of what there is was created to shift and resettle squatters once they were there, not to reduce the necessity for squatting. Perhaps the only defence we can make of Chandigarh here, and it is a weak one, is that this is not a problem any other major city in the developing world has solved either: the logistics of preventing, removing or shifting squatter settlements in any decisive way

are – assuming minimal humanity – simply too daunting; so they become an implicitly accepted feature of the urban scheme, and evolve their own kind of interface with the political system and civic authorities; they are in fact internally organized and regulated, but by means that are at best quasi-legal. Perhaps nothing but development and prosperity, to the point where people do not think it worth their while to live in such conditions for the sake of a livelihood in the city, will abolish them. In the meantime the authorities may have no option but to negotiate a path between the hostility of the majority of vocal citizens and considerations of what is possible and not inhumane, both sides having a political voice: it is a very empirical process.

It is my impression that very probably, relative to other Indian cities, Chandigarh is not unpopular even with its poor:

'Asha ... sells roasted groundnuts at the Plaza in Sector 17. She was born and brought up in Chandigarh. She acknowledges the better opportunities [in] Ludhiana. But "Ludhiana is so dirty. Cannot think of living there." Asha lives in a "jhugg" [i.e. a hut in a squatter colony] in Sector 25.'²⁰

Asha does not complain that Chandigarh makes no provision for housing the likes of her: no Indian city does anyway. The Administration has failed to wish away the large informal sector sustaining itself on sundry useful street occupations – roadside teashops, shoe maintenance, bicycle repair, itinerant vending and the like. Writing in 1982, Madhu Sarin recorded that:

'A majority of the senior officials view non-plan [i.e. informal sector] enterprises as an underworld of anti-social elements... Although it is recognized that many resort to such occupations because of poverty... there is a strong impression that a majority have high incomes... [Thus] they harass them to the point where they are unable to consolidate in anyone location, particularly a "desirable" one.'²¹

Despite periodic fits of 'enforcement', such attitudes have softened over the years with the experience of failure to evict the informal sector coupled with the limitations imposed by a political system that does empower all interests to some extent.

We might see the problem as not whether Chandigarh needs to change – since it is changing anyway – but how to cope with, or respond to, the changes that are taking place. Firstly, leaving aside all other questions of the city's functionality, it will be necessary to take stock of its relationship to its geographical surroundings. The tidy suburbless square of the Master Plan, designed for 500,000 people, still gives us our mental picture of Chandigarh, partly because the political boundaries of the Union Territory of Chandigarh roughly accord with it (reflecting

the 'status quo' of 1966)²² and partly just because of its power as myth. This mythical Chandigarh is now actually but the nucleus of a much larger, irregularly shaped urban growth falling in three State jurisdictions, growing rapidly in several directions according to the different and uncoordinated plans of the States concerned (and to no plan at all, as regards the illegal urbanization of the surrounding villages and agricultural lands). The real city never strictly fitted the myth; now the area comprising Chandigarh and its environs including the suburban extensions built independently by Punjab and Haryana has a population of a million and a half. Some Chandigarh conservatives would still, Canute-like, halt what they see as a slum-laden tide engulfing Le Corbusier's sacred ten-mile-deep green agricultural periphery: every new development is still controversial, scandal is still made of it (not without reason) but there's no stopping the emergence, planned or unplanned, of a much larger and more populous 'Greater Chandigarh'. The States of Punjab and Haryana will have an interest in attracting new projects, investments and sources of tax revenue into their own parts of this agglomeration. It is reasonable to speculate that in times to come Le Corbusier's Chandigarh may only be the 'best address' in a much larger, less distinctive but more dynamic urban conglomeration: one thinks of New Delhi in the midst of Delhi.

So the city is in fact changing and evolving in response to the urbanizing pressures overtaking the country and the region and the consequent requirements and demands of a larger, more varied population; of changing tastes and life-styles; and of new economic opportunities which people want the freedom to exploit. The city's growth itself changes its character. There is a long history of gradual modification of the original plans and gradual relaxation of the original strict controls, allowing a few non-residential uses in residential areas; allowing the subdivision of shops in certain areas; constructing a new kind of covered market, with small booths facing internal roads, to sell to 'rehriwallas'²³ at subsidized rates in the hope of resettling them; allowing weekly vegetable markets; even the emergence of new, lower-cost residential areas if only as the result of efforts to resettle squatters. This is a continuous process with more demands and suggestions perpetually under discussion. The political process also, inevitably and rightly, enters into it: by the time Phase II (Sectors 30-47) was beginning to be developed in the early 1980s, it had become politically impossible to acquire and raze whole villages, as had been done for Phase I, so now four such 'urbanized' villages remain, as dense, congested, lively and un-tidy as anything in any Indian city, to break forever the pattern of the sectors they

fall in. In yielding ground, the Administration's objective is usually to contain the forces of change ('Thus far and no further!') but it finds itself in a state of unending strategic retreat. And as encroachments and violations of the by-laws multiply, with the numbers of their perpetrators, the rules by which the city was built begin to lose their sanctity. The city evolves through an incremental process of violation and defensive modification of its rules and begins very, very gradually to look and feel a little more like other Indian cities. Superficial changes (like the gradual breakdown of the controls on advertising) begin to prepare our minds for more radical, less reversible ones: pressure from the haves,

not the have-nots, may eventually compel some haphazard 'redensification' of private properties in the spacious older sectors, to cash in on land values; the visual controls, already deteriorating in practice, may one day be abandoned. As this process gathers momentum and its opponents (again very gradually) disappear from the scene, newer fashions in thought will begin to seem respectable. We may be reminded in the end of Le Corbusier's famous words of resignation when he saw what the residents of his housing area at Pessac had done to the Purist cubes he had designed for them a generation earlier: life is right, he said, and the architect wrong.

Fig 1 - The central chowk, Chandigarh

Fig 2 - Central Chandigarh

NOTES

- ¹ This is, I am told, changing under the present dispensation.
- ² Chandigarh is administered by the Central Government, while shared as their capital by the States of Punjab and Haryana; this unusual arrangement has worked well enough since the partition of the old Punjab in 1965.
- ³ The author was Adviser to the Administrator – in effect Chief Executive of the Chandigarh Administration, of which the Governor of Punjab is titular Administrator – from February 1997 to April 1999.
- ⁴ The term did not occur to me at the time: I heard it as a *cliché* much later.
- ⁵ The beds of seasonal streams that flow during the monsoon.
- ⁶ *Statute of the Land*.
- ⁷ A good account of it is to be found in Ravi Kalia, *Chandigarh: The Making of an Indian City*, Oxford University Press, Delhi 1987.
- ⁸ Quoted in Ravi Kalia, *op. cit.* pp.28-29.
- ⁹ Jaspreet Takhar (ed.), *Celebrating Chandigarh*, Mapin, 2002, p. 194. These are the proceedings of the Conference Celebrating Chandigarh: 50 Years of the Idea, held in Chandigarh in January 1999.
- ¹⁰ At the insistence of Charles Correa, a full-scale mock-up was erected at the site for the Conference Celebrating Chandigarh held in January, 1999: I hope that is not the closest we ever get to constructing it.
- ¹¹ The Governor's residence.
- ¹² *Chandigarh Tribune*, August 31, 2001.
- ¹³ *Ibid.*
- ¹⁴ Particularly the northern, older and more sought-after sectors.
- ¹⁵ Charles Correa in *Celebrating Chandigarh*, p.196.
- ¹⁶ Slum Areas (Improvement and Clearance) Act, 1956.
- ¹⁷ Remarks like Correa's provoked howls of protest after the Conference Celebrating Chandigarh in 1999, and the most appalling accusations of bad faith.
- ¹⁸ *Statute of the Land*.
- ¹⁹ See Madhu Sarin, *Urban Planning in the Third World: The Chandigarh Experience*, Mansell Publishing, London 1982. Despite its obtrusive ideological perspective, this is a really valuable book that ought to have had more influence in Chandigarh.
- ²⁰ Rajivlochan et al., *Chandigarh Lifescape: Brief Social History of a Planned City*, Chandigarh Perspectives, 1999.
- ²¹ *Ibid.*
- ²² In 1966, with the partitioning of Punjab into

(mainly) the new States of Punjab and Haryana, Chandigarh became a Union Territory, functioning as the capital of both States but itself administered by the Central Government. This arrangement continues.

²³ Costermongers

KEYWORDS

Le Corbusier, Chandigarh, City Centre, preservation, intervention

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